

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

HTRA1 (HtrA serine peptidase 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

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Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Benjamin Siciliano ¹ , Qianjin Li ¹ , Katerina Gospodinova ² , Ishita Ajith ² , Jesse Wiley ³ , Gregory Cary ⁴ , YCharOS ⁵ , Souvika Bakshi ² , Richard Nwakamma ¹ , Elizabeth Zoeller ¹ , Ranjita Betarbet ¹ , Vittorio Katis ² , Allan Levey ¹ , Paul Brennan ² , Haiyan Fu ¹ , Zhexing Wen ¹ , and the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center
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Affiliations	¹ Emory University, Atlanta, GA, USA ² Centre for Medicines Discovery, University of Oxford, Oxford, United Kingdom ³ Sage Bionetworks, Seattle, WA, USA ⁴ The Jackson Laboratory, Bar Harbor, ME, USA ⁵ YCharOS, McGill University, Montreal, Canada

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TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.84 (rank #691, 97.2th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target’s general relevance to Alzheimer’s Disease, and is the sum of the target’s Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.84 out of 5 (rank #691, 97.2th percentile). The individual score components include 1.98 of 3 for genetics, and 1.86 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of HTRA1 protein is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. HTRA1 is annotated to GO terms from the Apoptosis, Structural Stabilization, and Proteostasis domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer’s Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD).

The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. The expression of HTRA1 is confidently detected in oligodendrocyte precursor cells (OPC),

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
3.838	691	97.22	1.981	1.858

oligodendrocytes, microglia, astrocytes, and some inhibitory neuron sub-types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

HTRA1 is a serine protease of the trypsin family, as discussed below. The scientific data suggests that HTRA1 localizes to plaques, increases expression in tandem with AD pathology, and cleaves APP, Tau, and APOE, supporting its potential involvement in either promoting or resisting AD-linked disease process (see below of citations). This TEP project intends to provide the scientific community with high quality resources that may help identify the role of HTRA1 in AD-linked biology. This TEP includes bioinformatic analysis, protein structural information and purified protein, and antibodies validation testing for HTRA1 specificity. We hope these resources help promote future HTRA1 investigations.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

HTRA1 is serine protease within the trypsin family (1,2) that acts upon a multitude of substrates, including extracellular matrix proteins and growth factor complexes (1). HTRA1 can regulate growth factor signalling through varied mechanisms that either promote or repress signalling—for example, it can cleave the pro-form of TGFbeta, the TGFbeta receptor, or other binding complex proteins (3–7), highlighting the diversity of roles that HTRA1 proteolysis can mediate, even within a single pathway. Unbiased TMT proteomics of amyloid plaques derived from early onset AD (EOAD) and trisomy 21 patients, demonstrate high levels of HTRA1 within the plaque complex (8), supporting the hypothesis that HTRA1 may be significantly associated with AD pathogenesis. In large scale proteomic studies looking for associations between disease state and protein abundance, HTRA1 increases in mild cognitive impairment (MCI), and shifts to even higher levels in samples taken from AD patients (9). An examination of the 5XFAD mouse model of AD demonstrated a consistent finding, with age dependent increases in HTRA1 in the brains of the 5XFAD mice, coincident with pathological progression in the animal model (9). The association with disease state does not elucidate whether it plays a disease promoting process or represents an attempt at homeostatic rectification. Among the numerous HTRA1 targets is APOE (10,11), one of the strongest disease-linked genes in late onset AD (LOAD). Interestingly, HTRA1 cleavage of APOE generates small fragments of apolipoprotein that stimulate synaptic sprouting and neurite formation (12), suggesting that at least one HTRA1 cleavage substrate promotes synaptic integrity, supporting the possibility that HTRA1 may facilitate trophic homeostasis. Consistent with this speculation, other another group identified the HTRA1 proteolysis of APOE to be allele specific, with greater degradation occurring with APOE4 (the disease-linked allele) than APOE3 (11). Further linkage between HTRA1 and AD, is found in the role of HTRA1 in proteolytic processing of both APP derived fragments (13,14), potentially explaining the localization of HTRA1 at AD plaques as a plausible clearance mechanism, and Tau (14), suggesting a plausible role in regulating AD-associated pathogenesis.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

The YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for HTRA1. The YCharOS antibody characterization pipeline uses knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of available commercial antibodies for HTRA1 by immunoblot (Western blot) and immunoprecipitation. The cell line background was chosen based on the adequate expression of the target protein. Link to report: [YCharOS HTRA1 antibody characterization report](#).

Cell type specific expression:

Using anti-human HTRA1 antibody ab274322 as appears in the [YCharOS HTRA1 Antibody Characterization Report](#), HTRA1 expression was easily detected in human iPSC-derived astrocyte and microglia cell lysates but minimally detected in human iPSC-derived neuron cell lysates (Fig. 1). Distinct bands for HTRA1 were also seen in astrocyte conditioned media. See **Additional Information** for cell line information, iPSC differentiation protocols, and Western blot conditions.

Figure 1. Expression of HTRA1 in whole cell lysates (top) and media (bottom) across neurons (N), astrocytes (A), and microglia (M) derived from iPSC cell lines WTC11 (left) and F033K (right). Independent samples (n=2) were run in adjacent lanes.

Biological probe discovery:

- 1) **Immunodepletion of secreted protein in medium** : HTRA1 was immunoprecipitated from media conditioned with WTC11-derived neurons. HTRA1 was measured in eluate following immunoprecipitation by Western blot, and unbound HTRA1 was detected in flowthrough by Western blot (Fig. 2). See **Additional Information** for experimental information on immunoprecipitation and Western blotting.

Figure 2. Immunoprecipitation (IP) of HTRA1 using validated antibody ab274322 from WTC11 iPSC-derived neuron conditioned media. Western blot of eluted HTRA1 (top) and unbound HTRA1 in flowthrough (bottom) from media samples, n=3 technical replicates of single sample collection loaded in three adjacent lanes.

- 2) **Cell-based assays following immunodepletion**: To understand the impact of modulating HTRA1 on

cell function, we performed a small panel of assays on cells treated with anti-HTRA1 antibody. WTC11 iPSC-derived neurons were treated with anti-HTRA1 before measuring A β 40 and A β 42 in conditioned media (Fig. 3). iPSC-derived astrocytes were treated with anti-HTRA1 before measuring IL-6 in conditioned media (Fig. 4). Treatment with anti-HTRA1 slightly decreased A β 42 levels and A β 42:A β 40 in iPSC-neurons and nearly doubled IL-6 levels in iPSC-astrocytes. See **Additional Information** for experimental information.

Figure 3. Immunodepletion of HTRA1 from iPSC derived neurons by treatment with anti-HTRA1 antibody. A β 40 and A β 42 levels in WTC11 neuron conditioned media when treated with anti-HTRA1 antibody or IgG as measured by ELISA, n=3 independent experiments * p <0.05, ** p <0.01, and ns= p >0.05.

Figure 4. Immunodepletion of HTRA1 from iPSC derived astrocytes by treatment with anti-HTRA1 antibody. IL-6 levels in WTC11 astrocyte conditioned media when treated with anti-HTRA1 antibody or IgG as measured by ELISA, n=2 independent experiments * p <0.05.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of HTRA1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

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ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Methods

Cell line information

The familial Alzheimer's disease (fAD) iPSC line (F033K) was previously generated from fibroblasts of a patient carrying the APP V717I (London) mutation (15). The well-characterized WTC11 iPSC line (16) and the F033K line were cultured in mTeSR1 medium (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 85850) on cell culture treated dishes coated with Geltrex LDEV-Free Reduced Growth Factor Basement Membrane Matrix (Gibco/Thermo Fisher Scientific; Cat. No. A1413201) diluted 1:100 in DMEM/F-12 (Gibco/Thermo Fisher Scientific; Cat. No. 11320033). Briefly, mTeSR1 was replaced every other day or every day once 50% confluent. When 80-90% confluent, cells were passaged, which entailed the following: aspirating media, washing with DPBS, incubating with ReLeSR (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0484) at RT for 3 minutes, aspirating ReLeSR, and incubating at 37°C for 10 minutes, resuspending in mTeSR1 supplemented with 10nM Y-27632 dihydrochloride ROCK inhibitor (Tocris; Cat. No. 125410), counting, and plating onto Matrigel-coated plates at desired number.

iPSC differentiation protocols

Astrocytes: Human iPSC-derived astrocytes (iAs) were generated as previously described (17). Briefly, iPSCs were plated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates and infected with rtTA, SOX9, and NFIB lentivirus. On Day 0, medium was replaced with fresh mTeSR-1 medium containing 2.5 µg/mL doxycycline. From Day 1-7, iAs were cultured in expansion medium (DMEM/F12, 10% FBS, 1% N2, 1.25 µg/mL puromycin, 200 µg/mL Hygromycin) and gradually transitioned to FGF medium (Neurobasal, 2% B27, 1% NEAA, 1% GlutaMax, 1% FBS, 8 ng/mL FGF, 5 ng/mL CNTF, 10 ng/mL BMP4, 200 µg/mL Hygromycin) by Day 7. On Day 7, iAs were dissociated using Accutase for 10 minutes, and replated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates in FGF medium. From Day 9, FGF medium was changed to Maturation medium (1:1 DMEM/F12 and Neurobasal, 1% N2, 1% Na Pyruvate, 10 µg/µL NAC, 10 µg/µL hbEGF, 10 ng/mL CNTF, 10 ng/mL BMP4, 500 µg/mL cAMP) and half of the medium was changed every 2 to 3 days.

Neurons: Human iPSC-derived neurons (iNs) were generated as previously described (18). Briefly, iPSCs were plated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates and infected with rtTA and NGN2 lentivirus. On Day 0, medium was replaced with fresh mTeSR-1 medium containing 2.5 µg/mL doxycycline. From Day 1-3, iNs were cultured in K2B medium (KO DMEM, 15% KSR, 1% NEAA, 0.1% BME, 1% GlutaMax, 2 µg/ml doxycycline) and gradually transitioned to N2B medium (DMEM/F12, 1% GlutaMax, 1.5% dextrose, 1% N2, 2 µg/ml doxycycline, 1 µg/mL puromycin) by Day 3. On Day 4, iNs were dissociated using Accutase for 5 minutes, and replated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates in NBM medium (Neurobasal, 1% GlutaMax, 1.5% dextrose, 0.5% NEAA, 2% B27, 10 ng/ml BDNF, 10 ng/ml GDNF, 10 ng/ml CNTF, 2 µg/ml doxycycline, 1µg/mL puromycin) and half of the medium was changed every 2 to 3 days.

Microglia: Human iPSC-derived microglia-like cells (iMGL) were generated by first differentiating human iPSCs into hematopoietic progenitor cells using the STEMdiff Hematopoietic Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 05310) per manufacturer's instructions. Then, hematopoietic progenitor cells were differentiated into microglia using the STEMdiff Microglia Differentiation Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0019) and matured using STEMdiff Microglia Maturation Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0020) following the manufacturer's instructions.

Western blotting

Media were collected and spun at 5000 X g for 10 min. The supernatants were stored at -80°C. For Western blotting, 1/3 volume of 4x Laemmli protein sample buffer (BioRad, 1610747) was added to culture media. After boiling at 98°C for 5 min. For cell lysate collection, after removing media, cells were washed with PBS twice and collected in PBS with a cell scraper. Cells were spun at 3000 rpm for 5 min, and the supernatants were discarded. Cells were lysed in NP-40 buffer (1% nonidet P-40, 20 mM Tris (PH 7.4), 137 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol) with protease inhibitor (Sigma, P8340) and

phosphatase inhibitor (Sigma, P5726 and P0044). 1/3 volume of 4x Laemmli protein sample buffer (BioRad, #1610747) was added to lysate and samples were boiled at 98°C for 5 min. For Western blotting, cell culture media and lysates were separated on 10% Tris-glycine SDS-polyacrylamide gels. Proteins were transferred to 0.2 µm nitrocellulose membrane (BioRad, 1620112). The membrane was blocked with 5% non-fat milk for 1 hr and incubated with HTRA1 antibody (Abcam, ab274322) with 1:1000 dilution in TBST containing 3% BSA at 4°C overnight with gentle rocking. The membrane was washed with TBST for 10 mins three times and then incubated with the secondary antibody (Jackson ImmunoResearch Laboratories, #111-035-003) at 1:5000 at room temperature for 1 hr. After washing with TBST for 10 mins three times, images were taken with the ChemiDoc Imaging System (BioRad, 12003153).

Immunoprecipitation

Cell culture media were collected as described above for Western blotting. HTRA1 antibody (Abcam, ab274322) was added to media (0.75 µg/ml) and incubated at 4°C overnight with gentle rocking. Protein A/G beads (Santa Cruz, sc-2003) were prewashed with PBS twice and resuspended with lysis buffer after final wash. 30 µl slurry of resuspended beads were added to media which were incubated with the antibody. After two hours incubation at 4°C, beads were pelleted by centrifugation at 3,000 rpm (approximately 1,000xg) for 30 seconds at 4°C. The supernatants were collected to serve as flowthrough. Beads were washed with PBS 3 times. 30-50 ul 2x Laemmli sample buffer (BioRad, 1610737) was added to the beads pellet. After boiling for 5 minutes, samples can be stored at -20°C for Western blotting.

Immunodepletion in cell media

HTRA1 antibody (Abcam, ab274322) was added to media (0.75 µg/ml) with iPSC derived cells. The cells were further cultured for 3 days at 37°C in humidified conditions with 5% CO₂. Cell culture media were collected as described above for Western blotting. Prewashed protein A/G beads were added to media and incubated at 4°C for two hours. The following steps are the same as immunoprecipitation for cell media described above.

Measurement of Aβ and IL-6

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits specific for human Aβ₄₀ and Aβ₄₂ (Invitrogen: #KHB3482 and #KHB3441) and IL-6 (R&D Systems: #QK206) were used to quantify Aβ species and IL-6 according to the manufacturer's instructions. Results were expressed as percentages of the isotype control. The means from duplicate measurements are presented.

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